

3D live cell imaging: study of inter- and intracellular signalling induced by bitter molecules in tongue cell spheroids

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Abstract

Tissue complexity is not well represented in a flat 2D environment. In particular, proliferation rates and cellular phenotypes are altered, intercellular communication is lost or severely affected and signalling molecules do not have to diffuse through several cell layers to reach their target. Spheroids allow to investigate cell signalling in a 3D structure with intact cell-to-cell communication. However, there are challenges hampering 3D live-cell imaging including: (i) the stabilization of spheroids under perfusion conditions, (ii) the recording of many z-planes at high spatio-temporal resolution, and (iii) the complexity of data analysis.

Here, we addressed these issues using spheroids made with human-papillae derived tongue cells (HTC-8), immortalized and engineered to express a green-fluorescent genetically-encoded Ca²⁺ (G-GECO) sensors. By confocal and Light Sheet Fluorescence Microscopy (LSFM) we measured quantitatively intracellular Ca²⁺ changes upon acute application of gustatory bitter substances. We developed a simple and robust live-cell imaging perfusion setup for confocal as well as LSFM that granted spheroid stabilization and high-resolution microscopy in many z-planes at high spatio-temporal resolution.

With this approach we could show that Ca²⁺ transients induced by saccharin appeared in the whole spheroid and required extracellular Ca²⁺. However, the responses differed between the border and the centre of the spheroids, with larger and faster response in the outer region. Furthermore, ATP-mediated intercellular communication was found to play a major role in the generation of compound-evoked Ca²⁺ transients, suggesting the presence of an ATP-mediated positive autocrine/paracrine communication in HTC-8 spheroids.

In summary, the presented approach permits the study of fast inter- and intracellular signalling in 3D spheroid cultures upon compounds perfusion.

Keywords: taste, signalling, calcium imaging, optical biosensors, 3D spheroids

Introduction

Sweet and bitter compounds present in food are sensed by specialized differentiated taste cells, called “receptor cells”. They are located in taste buds, onion-like structures present in tongue papillae, receiving afferent innervation. Activation of sweet and bitter receptors in receptor cells induces intracellular Ca²⁺ signals that lead at the end to ATP release, necessary to communicate with afferent nerve terminals and also with other taste bud cells. Measurement of Ca²⁺ responses in taste cells is, therefore, a widely used read-out to evaluate gustatory responses and allows to determine the potency of receptor ligands. However, so far Ca²⁺ responses have been measured either in rodent or recombinant cells [1], which pose limitations wherefore results cannot be necessarily transferred to human. Thus, our aim was to develop a new approach to study gustatory human responses *in vitro*. For this purpose, a stably proliferating cell line (HTC-8) derived from human fungiform papillae [2], was engineered to stably express a genetically encoded Ca²⁺ sensor (G-GECO) and used to produce spheroids by a liquid overlay technique. These spherical cell-aggregates, of about 300 µm in diameter, were then used for live-cell imaging experiments with confocal and light-sheet microscopy. The challenge of stabilizing them during acute dynamic perfusion was addressed with cheap and easy set-up configurations, which allowed time-course recording of fluorescence changes with stability and high spatial resolution. The analysis took in account spatial differences in the response, showing that bitter-induced Ca²⁺ transients are faster and stronger in the outer spheroid region, and require ATP-mediated intercellular communication.

Experimental

HTC-8 cells expressing G-GECO were generated by lentiviral transduction of pLV-Ubic-G-GECO-Puro vector, and cultured as described previously [1, 3]. For spheroid generation, 5000 cells/well were plated and centrifuged in 96-well ULA plates (Greiner). HTC-8-G-GECO spheroids were used for live cell imaging at 5-7 days of *in vitro* culture. For confocal microscopy 3 spheroids/well were placed in µ-Slide III 3D perfusion chamber (Ibidi) in imaging control buffer [1, 3]. Gelatine nonwoven CL130 Scaffoldene pads (Freudenberg) were cut and

placed on spheroids for stabilisation. Once closed, the slides were connected to a gravity-driven custom-made perfusion system. Exchange of solution in the μ -well required 5-15 s. Spheroids were imaged using an inverted Leica TCS SP8 confocal microscope equipped with a water immersion 20x/0.75 objective. A single z-plane, at about 20-40 μ m spheroid depth, was acquired every 5 s upon excitation at 488 nm, and detection at 500-550 nm. For LSM, spheroids were mounted with 0.5 % low melting agarose in a U-shaped glass capillary (Hilgenberg), fixed in a glass bottom dish (Ibidi). Exchange of the buffer occurred in 3.5-5 min. LSM imaging used a Leica TCS SP8 DLS vertical turn light-sheet microscope equipped with Leica HC APO L 10x/0.3 W objective. Spheroids were optically sectioned over 80-90 μ m depth at 3.7 μ m z-steps distance. Sodium saccharin (Sigma), ATP disodium salt (Roche) and Suramin sodium salt (Sigma) were dissolved in control buffer, and osmolarity was adjusted.

Ca^{2+} responses were analysed with ImageJ. The ImageJ erosion function was applied to obtain four concentric rings (R1-R4 from border to centre). The change in fluorescence (ΔF) was normalized to the value before stimulation (F_0) as followed $\Delta F/F_0 = (F - F_0)/F_0$, and plotted as a function of time. The peak intensity was the maximum $\Delta F/F_0$ within the stimulation window. Peak amplitudes were plotted versus the log of saccharin concentrations to obtain a dose-response curve. T_{Peak} and T_{Slope} defined respectively the time interval from the stimulation to the time of the peak or to the onset of the response. $T_{\text{Slope-Peak}}$ was defined as the interval from the onset to the maximum intensity. Bar graphs show mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). Statistics were performed using one-way ANOVA or Student t-test. For details, see [3].

Results and discussion

HTP-8 cells were previously shown to express TAS2R8, R31 and R43, encoding the membrane-located bitter receptors for saccharin [1]. Therefore, we investigated saccharin-induced Ca^{2+} response in HTC-8-G-GECO spheroids. Stabilization of the spheroids within the μ -well of the perfusion chamber was achieved by covering them with a collagen-mash (Scaffolene) that gets transparent when wet and is soft, allowing optimal stabilization without hampering diffusion or spheroid structure. Confocal live-cell imaging revealed that saccharin elicited Ca^{2+} responses that required extracellular Ca^{2+} (data not shown) [3]. We observed that the evoked Ca^{2+} transients were not uniform since their amplitudes and kinetics differed between the spheroid border and the inner regions. Analysing the Ca^{2+} changes in four concentric regions of interest, named “rings”, (Figure 1. A-B) confirmed that

Figure 1: Saccharin response in HTC-8-G-GECO spheroids. Representative confocal experiment of a HTC-8-G-GECO spheroid perfused first with control solution (A) and then with saccharin 5 mM (B). Color code represents fluorescence intensity. Image depth 30 μ m. Scale bar: 100 μ m (C) Dose-response curves were measured in the four concentric rings (R1-R4). EC_{50} : R1=1.06 mM, R2=1.50 mM, R3=1.67 mM and R4=1.46 mM. (D-F) Mean time-course traces responses to saccharin 0.5-5-10 mM in the four rings. Quantitative fluorescence analysis of Peak Intensity (G), Time to Peak (H), Time to Slope (i), and Time Slope to Peak (J) for responses elicited by saccharin (5 mM) stimulation in the four rings. Mean \pm SEM ($n \geq 5$ spheroids). ANOVA.

at all the concentrations tested, the Ca^{2+} transients started earlier, reached a larger peak in a shorter time in the outer ring (R1) (Figure 1 D-I). Consistently, dose-response curves measured in the four rings (R1-R4), showed decreasing sensitivity and potency when moving from the border toward the centre (Figure 1 C). Since the time from the onset to the peak was comparable in all rings, likely these differences are not due to diverse intracellular mechanisms of Ca^{2+} signal generation (Figure 1 J). Furthermore, such differences are evident even at single-cell level and do not depend on a reduced concentration of saccharin in the spheroid core due to diffusion (for data, see [3]).

Since ATP is the major neurotransmitters within the taste bud, we investigated whether HTP-8-G-GECO cells respond to it and whether ATP could play a paracrine/autocrine role in the spheroid. Indeed, ATP at a saturating concentration (1 mM), evoked Ca^{2+} transients with an amplitude comparable to that of saccharin (20 mM) (Figure 2 A, D), and the regional differences were evident as well. Nevertheless, the kinetic differed between the two compounds, as ATP-responses had a much shorter onset (Figure 2 E). Saccharin responses were largely reduced by co-application of the purinergic antagonist Suramin (Figure 2 C, F) suggesting that ATP released by HTC-8-G-GECO cells contributed to amplify bitter-induced Ca^{2+} signals. This effect seemed to be comparable in all spheroid regions, since the reduction of fluorescence was homogeneous (Figure 2 G).

Figure 2: Purinergic signaling is involved in the saccharin response. Mean fluorescence changes over time, in the 4 rings, with ATP (1 mM) (A) or saccharin (20 mM) stimulation (B). (C) Plot of fluorescence changes over time upon perfusion of saccharin (10 mM) alone or in the presence of the purinergic antagonist Suramin (100 μM). Comparison of the responses between ATP and saccharin for (D) Peak Intensity and (E) Time to Peak. (F) Whole-spheroid mean fluorescence changes upon perfusion as indicated in the x-axis. (G) Percentage of fluorescence reduction induced by Suramin. Data are normalised to saccharin response. Mean \pm SEM ($n \geq 5$ spheroids). ANOVA and Students *t*-test.

Since confocal live-imaging limited the acquisition to only one z-plane due to poor time resolution, we took advantage of LSM, which allowed to scan, within the same time frame (4-5 sec), 30 z-planes over a 100 μm depth, without losing fluorescence intensity with increasing depth [3]. For experiments with acute stimulation, the perfusion set-up needed to be adapted, since the samples had to be positioned between two mirrors, which are submerged in the recording solution. Therefore, the spheroids were embedded with agarose in an open U-shaped glass capillary, which was positioned in a glass-bottom plate, where tubes for in- and out-flow were also fixed. Perfusion with ATP (1 mM) elicited an increase in fluorescence, similarly to what observed with confocal microscopy. The advantage was that we could observe the time-course changes in multiple planes instead of only one. The Ca^{2+} changes were measured in each plane and were plotted over time and spheroid depth (Figure 3 A, B). The analysis confirmed what we observed already with confocal microscopy: ATP-induced Ca^{2+} transients were larger in the outer z-planes, and decreased progressively with increasing depth (Figure 3 B). The peak response was however delayed compared to the confocal experiments, likely due to the larger volume of the recording chamber (ml, instead of μl).

Live-imaging with LSM, which allow to scan 3D cell cultures at high speed maintaining cellular resolution and optimal signal-to-noise-ratio even in the deeper planes, may be particularly advantageous in case of irregular

structures, cocultures and focal stimulation. However, the analysis of this large amount of data, not only with quantitative but also with spatial and time information, will require further development.

Figure 3: Time course of ATP response acquired by LSFM. (A) Images of a representative HTC-8 G-GECO spheroid at different z-depth, in control buffer and upon stimulation with ATP (1 mM). Scale bar, 50 μM. (B) The fluorescence change was plotted over time and depth (z-plane), for the experiment as in A-B. The mean fluorescence was normalised to the signal before stimulation.

Conclusion

In summary, we showed that the HTC-8-G-GECO cell line, derived from human tongue papillae cells and engineered to express a genetically encoded Ca^{2+} sensor, could be used to produce spheroids that respond to the taste compounds. As read-out, we used live-cell Ca^{2+} imaging. In this three-dimensional structure, the cells find a more physiological environment, as shown by the regional differences in Ca^{2+} response, and the involvement of endogenous ATP in the generation of bitter-induced Ca^{2+} signals. These effects would be neglected in 2D cultures and with static drug application. Furthermore, we showed that it is possible to study by LSFM Ca^{2+} dynamics in the whole spheroid without losing time- and spatial-resolution even in acute perfusion condition. Our approach thus opens new possibilities to study gustatory responses in human-derived cells that, grown in a 3D structure, retain cell-cell interaction. Additionally, the spheroids mimic a native tissue in that the compounds have to diffuse through multiple cell layers to reach their target. While confocal and LSFM allowed to study Ca^{2+} signals with single-cell resolution [3], HTC-8-G-GECO spheroids may also be applied to develop high-throughput gustatory screenings, since they are easy and cheap to be produced.

References

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